

AquaPLAN

Aquatic Pollution from Light and
Anthropogenic Noise: **Management
of Impacts on Biodiversity**

D1.4 Data Management Plan – 1st release

28/06/24 Version 1.3

Lead author: *Elena Maggi, Università di Pisa*

elena.maggi@unipi.it

Public¹

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Author(s)	Elena Maggi (UNIFI) Alessandro Marchetti (UNIFI) Mascha Stroobant (UNIFI)
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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The purpose of this Deliverable is data management, particularly setting up and updating a Data Management Plan. This document assists consortium members on high-quality data management in compliance with funder requirement:

- strategy of data management;
- general measure of data management;
- summary of data expected and re-used in the project;
- application of FAIR principles to data produced during the project;
- handling other research outputs (digital like software or protocols and physical output);
- strategies for data storage, allocation of resources and data security;
- activity plan for data management.

The project Data Management Plan will be updated at later stages.

Disclaimer: The document does not in any way overrule the Grant Agreement (including its associated Annexes) and the Consortium Agreement.

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1. Introduction

In the AquaPLAN project, 6 EU and 7 non-EU international partners will perform research together in 6 (six) work packages over a period of 4 years. This does not only require good project management but also **well-organised data management**. This includes foremost the Data Management Plan (DMP), but also other work performed by the **Data Management Group** (DMP Group) as outlined in the next chapters. The Data Management Plan will particularly focus on developing strategies of data handling in line with the FAIR principle.

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** is part of work package WP1 as task T1.4. It will continue over the entire duration of the project with 3 main deliverables: the DMP at month 6, month 24 and month 48. All partners are involved in the data management. For T1.4, a DMP group is formed with one representative from each project partner at least. The DMP group will discuss open points on data management and will decide on common DMP strategies. This will be taken in agreement with legal data privacy regulations. We will here consult GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation of EU), the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA).

All partners will benefit from good data management as it provides them guidance on data storage, data publication, meta-data standards, and related aspects. During the project, the DMP group will also define standard file formats for sample data, including metadata to guarantee data usability for all partners and avoid data loss due to a lack of documentation.

We expect the production of new data from field investigations, laboratory investigations, data processing and visualisation, modelling and algorithms' development and application. We will also make use of existing data (see Table 1.2 and Table 1.6 of the DoA (Part B) in the GA) which will be clearly specified and distinguished from newly produced data.

In terms of data types and formats, we expect extensive datasets as listed in Table 1.9 of the DoA (Part B) in the GA (see also **Annex 6** of the present document).

For data produced during the project, we follow the “as open as possible but as closed as necessary” principle for data management. The DMP particularly focuses on strategies of data handling in line with the FAIR principle. Raw data storage (field investigations, laboratory investigations) will be managed by each group producing it using cloud or server solutions with back-ups and possibilities to share data between groups.

At mature status, results will be published, and data will be made findable and accessible by publication in trusted repositories including unique identifiers (DOIs). Processed observation data, software development and modelling results will be published either in the supplementary material along with a publication (having a DOI) or separately in a trusted data and software repositories, or both. However, licences for data sharing and re-use (e.g. Creative Commons, Open Data Commons) remain subject to the individual groups.

We will perform Intellectual property (IP) management for generated datasets specifically in Task 6.3 (WP6). The IP management will be led by ERINN and all partners.

The AquaPLAN consortium is aware of the obligation to protect those results that are expected to be commercially or industrially exploitable. AquaPLAN will adhere to ownership, access rights and IPR protection principles as defined in the GA and CA, following HEU principles. As part of the PDEC, the main IP protection and management rules and practical implementation processes were outlined and explained at the project kick-off meeting. AquaPLAN (SIB) will

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support IPR protection by assessing results, including their exploitation potential, as part of the KMKKT process (T6.3). In addition, an IP checklist will be implemented as part of the prior notice process for publications where publishing partners will be asked to confirm that there is nothing exploitable in their publication, which will be verified by SIB, with support from partners' technology transfer (TT) offices if needed. Partners' TT officers can assist partners in identifying results and innovations that may need protection; provide advice on the determination of results ownership, management of joint ownership granting of access rights, freedom to operate, patentability and the choice between patent and other procedures; and identify market risks and opportunities concerning the evolution of the solution, potential customers and/or existing and emerging competitors. Partners who are owners of results will ensure that adequate protective steps are taken before DEC activities, preventing unapproved public disclosure of results, tools, products and services. The 'Results Ownership List' (ROL) will be reported as part of D6.3.

2. General measures for data management

In the AquaPLAN project, 6 EU and 7 non-EU international partners will perform research activities and produce datasets that will need to be adequately managed. We anticipate that AquaPLAN will generate 24 new datasets constituting 1.27Tb of video, audio, images, documents, maps and databases.

2.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN ONLINE TOOL

The Data Management Plan will be in place over the entire period of the project. We make use of the online-tool DMP- online (<https://www.dcc.ac.uk/dmps>). The DMP in this online tool will be **regularly updated** and saved in the project administration repositories with related data. We will create 3 main versions:

- 1st version at M6, being part of this deliverable
- 2nd version at M24, being deliverable D1.4
- Final version at M48 at the end of the project, being deliverables D1.6

We use the Horizon Europe Template, Version 1.0 (05 May 2021) provided in the DMP-online tool. It provides a list of questions on the main topics:

- Data summary
- FAIR data
- Other research outputs
- Allocation of resources
- Data security
- Ethics
- Other issues

We address all these questions to outline the details of the DMP. This will be the content of the following sections which are structured following the main topics and providing the questions as well as our answers to them.

2.2 ADDITIONAL MEASURES OF DATA MANAGEMENT

We furthermore take a list of general measures to ensure high-quality data management.

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The key measure is the formation of a data management group where each project partner is represented. We will meet regularly (and will continue to do so), at intervals which will also depend on the status of the DMP. During meetings, we assess the status of the DMP, and assess the dissemination of data and their potential publication. We will assist researchers in the project to prepare the data according to project needs as well as following the FAIR principles. Each meeting will be documented including minutes being checked and approved by all participants. Meeting material and minutes will be stored in the AquaPLAN intranet (GoogleDrive) and will be available to all project partners throughout the entire project duration.

To assist project partners in preparing their data according to FAIR principles, we will make use of FAIRness assessment tools such as FAIRdat or SATIFYD (or other tools as recently evaluated by Krans et al. (2022)).

The DMP group will collaboratively setup data file templates (next step). This will be done aligned with metadata standards used in the project (see section 5). Using metadata standards of the individual disciplines guarantee that variables are exactly defined.

We will consult with the Research and Technology Transfer Services Department⁵ of UNIPI providing expert knowledge and guidance on the DMP as well as direct data management, e.g. handling of data storage solutions, data publication, metadata standards, licences, and infrastructural support for database setup.

2.3 DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION OF DATA

Owners of resulting research datasets are required to develop and implement a dissemination and exploitation strategy for such data. As a basic principle, it is vital to understand that the obligation to exploit results does not replace the obligation to disseminate results, and vice versa. Hence, there could be something to disseminate about the exploitation strategies for generated research datasets, provided that such data is not marked as confidential information according to the conditions established in Section 10 of the AquaPLAN Consortium Agreement (CA) (i.e. “Non-disclosure of information”).

Art. 16 of the GA stipulates that exploitation strategies may refer to post-project Research & Development (R&D) activities, the use of research data for the development and commercialization of products and services, and/or in standardisation activities. It is required that AquaPLAN partners balance open access & open data requirements with potential exploitation opportunities, in particular commercial ones. Thus, all datasets will be first checked for their exploitation potential before dissemination. Data underlying scientific publications will be made available without restrictions. For all other datasets, it will be decided on a case-by-case basis whether access can be granted without giving away sensitive information. For example, data whose release would limit the patentability of a result will not be made accessible to the public. In general, access will be as open as possible, but as restricted as necessary.

⁵ <https://euresearch.unipi.it/research-and-technology-transfer-services-directorate-university-of-pisa/>

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Along these lines, project partners may also request access rights to the owner of resulting research datasets under fair and reasonable conditions, whenever it is needed for the development and implementation of their exploitation plans.

This is stipulated in Art. 9.4.1 of the AquaPLAN CA:

“Access Rights to Results if Needed for Exploitation of a Party’s own Results shall be granted on Fair and Reasonable conditions and upon written bilateral agreement. Access Rights to Results for internal research and for teaching activities shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.”

According to Art. 17 of the GA, the research data generated in AquaPLAN must be disseminated effectively and by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium). Such means and conditions of the dissemination activities fall under the responsibility of the owner of the resulting research dataset, with support and guidelines established by the project’s DMP subgroup.

The GA has also established the obligation to share research data (and metadata) underlying (peer-reviewed) scientific publications, in accordance to the Open Science (OS) paradigm outlined in Art. 1.2.9 and the Annex 5 of Art. 17.4 on open access publications, which states:

“The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results.”

Such research data can also refer in this context to relevant data as background, whenever it is needed to validate the analytical activities described in a (peer-reviewed) scientific publication generated in AquaPLAN.

Moreover, AquaPLAN partners have agreed during the proposal development to adhere to Open Science principles with regard to research data generated (as result) in the project. This applies not only to the data and metadata needed to validate results in scientific publications, but also to other curated and/or raw data and metadata that may be required for validation purposes or with re-use value. All legal requirements are described in Art. 17 of the GA (Open science: research data management):

- The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and by taking all of the following actions:
- establish a Data Management Plan ('DMP') (and regularly update it)
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:
 - be against the beneficiary’s legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or

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- be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP
- provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC-0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

2.4 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTIES AND RIGHTS

The balance between the project's openness and confidentiality requirements for research data generated within the project will be discussed on a case-by-case basis by project partners. It is, however, evident that whenever a generated research dataset has potential commercial or industrial value, the owner of such a dataset must take all pertinent measures to protect it, in line with the obligations of the Grant Agreement (GA). Specifically, Art. 16 of the GA details the obligation to protect results:

“Beneficiaries which have received funding under the grant must adequately protect their results — for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage — if protection is possible and justified, taking into account all relevant considerations, including the prospects for commercial exploitation, the legitimate interests of the other beneficiaries and any other legitimate interests. “

A research dataset is any organised collection of data defined by a theme or category that reflects what is being measured, observed, or monitored. In this regard, an original research dataset may be protected in Europe by Copyright Law. This means that the developer of such a dataset may claim an exclusive right for 70 years (this duration can differ in non-EU countries) to exclude others from using, copying, and exploiting this dataset without prior given consent.

Also, partners may claim the sui generis right for the protection of original databases for a period of 15 years. The sui generis database right protects a database, which is defined as follows in Article 1 (2) of the EU Database Directive (96/9/EC):

“[...] a collection of independent works, data or other materials arranged in a systematic or methodical way and individually accessible by electronic or other means.”

(DIRECTIVE 96/9/EC OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL (March 1996) on the legal protection of databases. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A31996L0009>)

Furthermore, research datasets generated by partners within the project can also be marked as “Confidential Information” according to Section 10 of the CA, with the purpose to limit

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access for disclosure outside of the consortium. Such restriction applies not only for the duration of project implementation, but also for a period of 5 years after the project has ended.

Taking all this into consideration, all partners are highly encouraged to mark their data as confidential whenever it might be needed for the implementation of their exploitation strategies.

(Joint) ownership claims and further suitable protection measures (e.g. IPR) are analysed and presented in WP6 (Plan for the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC)).

3. Data summary

See below the main questions and answers related to the AquaPLAN Data Summary.

WILL YOU RE-USE ANY EXISTING DATA AND WHAT WILL YOU RE-USE IT FOR?

Data will be reused in the project. The two main sources of existing data reused in AquaPLAN are data from preliminary investigations at the project field sites as well as databases on microbiological and genetic information. Details on the reused data sets are selected in a table "DMP_Data_Reused_VX.xlsx" being accessible by all Consortium members. The current version is added to the Annex. The table outlines type and description of the data, as well as owner, source, formats, software required, maximum size, number of data files, purpose of use in the AquaPLAN project, metadata standards, storage location, linked publications, accessibility and licence.

WHAT TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA WILL THE PROJECT GENERATE OR RE-USE?

Data types and formats of reused data can be found in the table "DMP_Data_Reused_V1.xlsx" (in the Annex). A similar table "DMP_Data_Produced_V1.xlsx" is set up containing all data-management relevant aspects. As soon as data is produced during the project, the information on the data sets will be specified in the table. At this early state of the project no new data sets have yet been produced. We foresee research data to be newly produced in the project of the following origins with types and formats:

- Laboratory experimental (raw) data on
 - analytical data
 - (additional) numerical lab data
 - lab journal and protocolsFormats: csv/.biom/.fastq/.fasta/.xlsx/.txt/.doc/.docx/hand written notes
- Field - experimental data:
 - site descriptions, like sedimentary descriptions, hydrological parameters, biogeochemical conditions,
 - coordinates of sampling pointsFormats: csv/.xlsx/.txt/.doc/.docx/handwritten notes
- Numerical data/Processed data:
 - statistical output data & results visualisationFormat: .csv/.tsv/.tiff/.jpeg/.png/.pdf/.svg/.rmd/.RData/.qmd/.netCDF

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- Software implementation data
Format: .r/.py/.sh
- Simulation output
Format: .vtk, .csv, .pdf
- Non-scientific data produced in the project include documents on:
 - Activity plans, project descriptions, contracts, templates and guidelines, meeting protocols, presentations
 - DMP
 - AquaPLAN website

WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE DATA GENERATION OR RE-USE AND ITS RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT?

The purpose of each data set is specified in the tables "DMP_Data_Reused.xlsx" and "DMP_Data_Produced.xlsx" (in the Annex).

The data will be interpreted in combination with the metadata to understand the impacts of light and noise pollution. This also includes statistical analysis (processed data) and modelling (numerical data). All these data will provide new insights. They will be used to find solutions for reducing these impacts which is the purpose of the project.

WHAT IS THE EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA THAT YOU INTEND TO GENERATE OR RE-USE?

The number of files and size of each data set is specified in the tables "DMP_Data_Reused.xlsx" and "DMP_Data_Produced.xlsx" (in the Annex).

WHAT IS THE ORIGIN/PROVENANCE OF THE DATA, EITHER GENERATED OR RE-USED?

The origin of each data set is specified in the tables "DMP_Data_Reused.xlsx" and "DMP_Data_Produced.xlsx" (in the Annex).

The research data (newly) generated during the project will origin from research performed by the project partners through:

- experiments (raw data)
- interpretations/visualisations of experimental data (processed data)
- implementation of algorithms (data interpretation methods)
- modelling output (predictions based on observation data)
- documentation data produced by researchers (manuscripts)

TO WHOM MIGHT YOUR DATA BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY'), OUTSIDE YOUR PROJECT?

- other researchers
- stakeholders
- public companies

4. Fair Data

4.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA: WILL DATA BE IDENTIFIED BY A PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER?

All research data sets produced during the project will be findable through a unique identifier (UID). Data will either be published directly with a persistent identifier (DOI), in repositories/databases providing UIDs) or along a scientific publication (with DOI), e.g. in the supporting material or with link to an open archive.

We foresee for the different types of research data during the project:

- Experimental (raw) data: direct publication of the data set (with DOI) or deposition into a public repository providing unique identifier (e.g. sequence accession numbers).
- Processed experimental data: published in scientific articles.
- Numerical data: direct publication of the data set (with DOI).

MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA: WILL RICH METADATA BE PROVIDED TO ALLOW DISCOVERY? WHAT METADATA WILL BE CREATED? WHAT DISCIPLINARY OR GENERAL STANDARDS WILL BE FOLLOWED? IN CASE METADATA STANDARDS DO NOT EXIST IN YOUR DISCIPLINE, PLEASE OUTLINE WHAT TYPE OF METADATA WILL BE CREATED AND HOW?

Our newly created data sets will include comprehensive metadata. Given our consortium project involving diverse research groups, we anticipate various data types. However, it's important to note that specific metadata agreements cannot be finalised before the initial data collection. We plan to refine and provide more detailed metadata in the second release of the report

Details on the metadata standards will then be specified for each data set after publication in Table "DMP_Data_Produced.xlsx", Annex.

MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA: WILL SEARCH KEYWORDS BE PROVIDED IN THE METADATA TO OPTIMISE THE POSSIBILITY FOR DISCOVERY AND THEN POTENTIAL RE-USE?

Keywords will be provided in the metadata according to the scientific domain-discipline, each dataset is related with. In this way we can ensure that interested parties can find our datasets.

4.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE REPOSITORY: WILL THE DATA BE DEPOSITED IN A TRUSTED REPOSITORY?

The research data produced in the project will be accessible in trusted repositories. Following the terms of the Grant Agreement all data will be open access, unless it is for commercial

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exploitation or contrary to any other constraints by the data (co-)owner. In particular, site owners engaged in AquaPLAN can request the site data collected by the project to be confidential for safety and business reasons.

We will use the following trusted repository:

Zenodo being a general-purpose repository. Here a project specific community for AquaPLAN will be set up.

The consortium agreed on using the listed repositories with Zenodo as a major repository to bundle all project data.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE REPOSITORY: DOES THE REPOSITORY ENSURE THAT THE DATA IS ASSIGNED AN IDENTIFIER?

Yes, the mainly used repository (Zenodo) for our project provides by default an unique identifier (DOI) to every paper/data publication, ensuring the accessibility of our datasets on this platform.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE DATA: WILL ALL DATA BE MADE OPENLY AVAILABLE? IF CERTAIN DATASETS CANNOT BE SHARED (OR NEED TO BE SHARED UNDER RESTRICTED ACCESS CONDITIONS), EXPLAIN WHY, CLEARLY SEPARATING LEGAL AND CONTRACTUAL REASONS FROM INTENTIONAL RESTRICTIONS. NOTE THAT IN MULTI-BENEFICIARY PROJECTS IT IS ALSO POSSIBLE FOR SPECIFIC BENEFICIARIES TO KEEP THEIR DATA CLOSED IF OPENING THEIR DATA GOES AGAINST THEIR LEGITIMATE INTERESTS OR OTHER CONSTRAINTS AS PER THE GRANT AGREEMENT.

We follow the principle '**as open as possible but as closed as necessary**'. Most research data produced in the project will be openly accessible. Following the terms of the Grant Agreement (Annex 5) all data will be open access unless it is for commercial exploitation.

We currently expect that data produced solely by research groups of the consortium will be shared openly. Industry partners in the consortium indicated that opening specific data goes against their legitimate interests. Research includes field sampling at contaminated sites owned by third parties. Some of the gathered data will be subject to restrictions due to legal and contractual reasons. This includes:

- Protocols used to generate evolution data will be restricted due to commercial interests of industry partners. They will not be accessible within the consortium nor outside the consortium. On a case-specific basis we will evaluate if it is possible to publish data-subsets, like part of the protocol.
- Data on adaptive laboratory evolution (key performance indicator, diversity data - sequencing data, pictures - protocols used to generate the evolution data) will be restricted as this is commercially sensitive information.
- Restrictions may apply to data collected by AquaPLAN partners as well as data from 3rd parties (i.e. contaminated field site owners) when there is no consent for public disclosure of such data. We will consider making part of the data available or after anonymising site specific data. The process will be evaluated in adherence to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

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When a produced dataset applies to restricted access conditions, these will be explained and put into context with constraints as per the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement (4.5 GDPR compliance) in the detailed data description in the Table of produced data (Annex).

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – DATA: IF AN EMBARGO IS APPLIED TO GIVE TIME TO PUBLISH OR SEEK PROTECTION OF THE INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY (E.G. PATENTS), SPECIFY WHY AND HOW LONG THIS WILL APPLY, BEARING IN MIND THAT RESEARCH DATA SHOULD BE MADE AVAILABLE AS SOON AS POSSIBLE.

Time embargos for data publication or protection of intellectual property (e.g. patents) are not expected for most of the produced research data.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – DATA: WILL THE DATA BE ACCESSIBLE THROUGH A FREE AND STANDARDISED ACCESS PROTOCOL?

As we plan to publish research data in established repositories, there will be a free and standardised access protocol.

For instance, data published in the Zenodo community can be accessed directly through downloading using the DOI and link.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – DATA: IF THERE ARE RESTRICTIONS ON USE, HOW WILL ACCESS BE PROVIDED TO THE DATA, BOTH DURING AND AFTER THE END OF THE PROJECT?

For produced research data, which is subject to restrictions on use, the data set owner will manage the access to the data. For restricted data sets we use the storage facilities specified below. They are all based on the principle of "need- to-know", meaning that only users who require access to the data for their work or tasks are authorised to access it. Every data user can access-log in these facilities with personal-institutional credentials. The owner of the restricted data set will decide how to share the data at different levels (e.g. read only, editor, co-owner) by providing access if requested.

We follow this procedure already for the project documentation/management data which is restricted to project members. Access is by registration on the google drive and authorization through the project manager.

When a dataset applies to restricted access conditions, access arrangements during and after the end of the project will be specified for the data set. A summary of that will be included in the Table "DMP_Data_Produced.xlsx" (Annex).

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – DATA: HOW WILL THE IDENTITY OF THE PERSON ACCESSING THE DATA BE ASCERTAINED?

Open-access datasets will not request the identity of the person accessing the data.

For restricted data sets we use the storage facilities specified below. They are all based on the principle of "need-to- know", meaning that only users who require access to the data for their work or tasks are authorised to access it. Every data user can access-log in these facilities with personal-institutional credentials. The owner of the data set will provide authorization.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – DATA: IS THERE A NEED FOR A DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE (E.G. TO EVALUATE/APPROVE ACCESS REQUESTS TO PERSONAL/SENSITIVE DATA)?

We do not expect personal or sensitive (research) data to be produced in the project. If data applies to restricted access this will be handled as outlined before. We thus do not see the need for a data access committee.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – METADATA: WILL METADATA BE MADE OPENLY AVAILABLE AND LICENCED UNDER A PUBLIC DOMAIN DEDICATION CC0, AS PER THE GRANT AGREEMENT? IF NOT, PLEASE CLARIFY WHY. WILL METADATA CONTAIN INFORMATION TO ENABLE THE USER TO ACCESS THE DATA?

We plan to make metadata openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0. At this stage, we do not foresee exceptions. In case of any exception, we will clarify why. We will use metadata community standards which will enable users to access the data and increase its findability.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – METADATA: HOW LONG WILL THE DATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AND FINDABLE? WILL METADATA BE GUARANTEED TO REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER DATA IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Published data will be available and findable long-term. This will be ensured by publishing it in trusted long-term maintained repositories and journals. The same holds for metadata.

MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE – METADATA: WILL DOCUMENTATION OR REFERENCE ABOUT ANY SOFTWARE BE NEEDED TO ACCESS OR READ THE DATA BE INCLUDED? WILL IT BE POSSIBLE TO INCLUDE THE RELEVANT SOFTWARE (E.G. IN OPEN-SOURCE CODE)?

We expect a large amount of data which requires software to access and efficiently read the data (e.g. sequencing data). This will be clearly documented and referenced in the metadata.

In case the needed software is open source and published (e.g. on GitHub, referenced with DOI), we will provide reference. If the software which is needed to access the data is developed alongside the data, it will be either published separately and referenced or included (if not published stand-alone). If the respective software is a commercial software or subject to restricted licence, it will not be possible to include it.

4.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

MAKING DATA AND METADATA VOCABULARIES, STANDARDS, FORMATS OR METHODOLOGIES WILL YOU FOLLOW TO MAKE YOUR DATA INTEROPERABLE TO ALLOW DATA EXCHANGE AND RE-USE WITHIN AND ACROSS DISCIPLINES? WILL YOU FOLLOW COMMUNITY-ENDORSED INTEROPERABILITY BEST PRACTICES? WHICH ONES?

As part of the project task DMP, we will collaboratively set up data file templates. We seek to use preferable formats not restricted to commercial software such as .txt/.pdf/.odt for Text, .csv/.Rdata for quantitative data, .jpg/.tiff for images.

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We will use metadata standards of the individual disciplines to guarantee that variables are exactly defined:

- Common metadata standards such as Datacite 4.0 & Dublin Core

The metadata standard is also depending on the repository where data will be preserved or shared. For instance, we will follow Zenodo's best effort principles. For making data interoperable this includes that metadata uses a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation such as the JSON scheme as internal representation of metadata.

The use of established metadata standards (including vocabularies, formats and methodologies) will also ensure that data is interoperable between project partner and other interested user.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE: IN CASE IT IS UNAVOIDABLE THAT YOU USE UNCOMMON OR GENERATE PROJECT SPECIFIC ONTOLOGIES OR VOCABULARIES, WILL YOU PROVIDE MAPPINGS TO MORE COMMONLY USED ONTOLOGIES? WILL YOU OPENLY PUBLISH THE GENERATED ONTOLOGIES OR VOCABULARIES TO ALLOW REUSING, REFINING OR EXTENDING THEM?

We do not expect the need to use uncommon ontologies nor are we planning to produce specific ontologies or vocabularies in this project.

MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE: DATA INTEROPERABLE: WILL YOUR DATA INCLUDE QUALIFIED REFERENCES⁶ TO OTHER DATA (E.G. OTHER DATA FROM YOUR PROJECT, OR DATASETS FROM PREVIOUS RESEARCH)?

Where applicable, produced research data will include qualified references to other data.

When research results/data builds up on each other, contextual knowledge will be provided. This holds e.g. for publication of results in scientific publications. Their used and produced data will be linked and with qualified references.

We will also use qualified references and cross-references to outline chains of data dependency and linked data. This will be facilitated by publishing the data within one Zenodo community which is planned for a large part of the data.

4.4 Increase data re-use

HOW WILL YOU PROVIDE DOCUMENTATION NEEDED TO VALIDATE DATA ANALYSIS AND FACILITATE DATA RE-USE (E.G. README FILES WITH INFORMATION ON METHODOLOGY, CODEBOOKS, DATA CLEANING, ANALYSES, VARIABLE DEFINITIONS, UNITS OF MEASUREMENT, ETC.)?

⁶ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

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Depending on the data type we will provide documentation which facilitates validation of data analysis and re-use. We will make use of readme files, codebooks and other measures for data management. Details on the methodology will be also documented in research papers. Most information will be provided in the method sections. We will also make use of Supporting Material which are common for scientific articles to provide detailed documentation if required and can be also uploaded to databases such as ResearchGate with more limited copyright constraint. We will try to encourage upload of specific files to Wikimedia Commons including appropriate descriptions containing links to related dataset, we will propose their insertion in specific **Wikipedia** articles. This way we ensure that research data can be validated and is reusable.

INCREASE DATA RE-USE: WILL YOUR DATA BE MADE FREELY AVAILABLE IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN TO PERMIT THE WIDEST RE-USE POSSIBLE? WILL YOUR DATA BE LICENSED USING STANDARD REUSE LICENCES, IN LINE WITH THE OBLIGATIONS SET OUT IN THE GRANT AGREEMENT?

We expect most of the data to be freely available in the public domain (open-access repositories) to allow re-use. We will only restrict data if it is subject to commercial use. Details on restricted data are outlined above.

Licences for data sharing and re-use remain subject to the project partners who produced the data. Data licensing will be arranged in accordance with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium following e.g. Creative Commons, Open Data Commons.

INCREASE DATA RE-USE: WILL THE DATA PRODUCED IN THE PROJECT BE USABLE BY THIRD PARTIES, IN PARTICULAR AFTER THE END OF THE PROJECT?

Openly published data will be usable by third parties, during and after the end of the project. This will apply to most of the processed data (results and visualisations) as well as developed software and simulation data.

Raw data produced during the project with restricted re-usability (depending on licence) will not be usable by third parties.

INCREASE DATA RE-USE: WILL THE PROVENANCE OF THE DATA BE THOROUGHLY DOCUMENTED USING THE APPROPRIATE STANDARDS?

The provenance of the data will be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards. This will be documented in READMEs, publications as well as in the metadata provided to the published data set on repositories. For instance, all data and metadata uploaded to Zenodo is traceable to a registered Zenodo user. But we will make sure that the original authors of the published work are described in the metadata as well.

Increase data re-use: Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

We will assure data quality through:

- data collection following the handbook for sampling and sample treatment
- sample analysis following a unified procedure (preferably all performed at the same lab)

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- use of data templates (developed during the project, WP1, T1.4)
- documentation of data with metadata following community standards as well as meta-data standards of targeted repositories for publication
- use of FAIRness assessment tools for improving FAIRness of data
- review of data.

INCREASE DATA RE-USE: FURTHER TO THE FAIR PRINCIPLES, DMPS SHOULD ALSO ADDRESS RESEARCH OUTPUTS OTHER THAN DATA, AND SHOULD CAREFULLY CONSIDER ASPECTS RELATED TO THE ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES, DATA SECURITY AND ETHICAL ASPECTS.

Besides the management of research data, we will also address the management of other research outputs, such as conference/workshop contributions, software development and physical research outputs.

We will also address aspects related to allocation of resources and data security. Ethical aspects do not apply here, as the research data is not related to personal data. See section 5.

5. Other aspects

5.1 OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

IN ADDITION TO THE MANAGEMENT OF DATA, BENEFICIARIES SHOULD ALSO CONSIDER AND PLAN FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS THAT MAY BE GENERATED OR RE-USED THROUGHOUT THEIR PROJECTS. SUCH OUTPUTS CAN BE EITHER DIGITAL (E.G. SOFTWARE, WORKFLOWS, PROTOCOLS, MODELS, ETC.) OR PHYSICAL (E.G. NEW MATERIALS, ANTIBODIES, REAGENTS, SAMPLES, ETC.).

The principles outlined in the DMP for research data will be similarly applied to digital research output (not being data), such as:

- protocols (D.3.1, D3.3, D4.1)
- algorithms (D3.2)
- models (D.3.7)

BENEFICIARIES SHOULD CONSIDER WHICH OF THE QUESTIONS PERTAINING TO FAIR DATA ABOVE, CAN APPLY TO THE MANAGEMENT OF OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS, AND SHOULD STRIVE TO PROVIDE SUFFICIENT DETAIL ON HOW THEIR RESEARCH OUTPUTS WILL BE MANAGED AND SHARED, OR MADE AVAILABLE FOR REUSE, IN LINE WITH THE FAIR PRINCIPLES.

The questions addressing the FAIR principles will be similarly applied to digital research output. This digital research output will be published, similar to data, in trusted repositories,

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with unique identifier (e.g. DOI), open access, with metadata and proper documentation (README etc.). Code and software will be created following good coding practice to make it reusable and interoperable. For instance, it will be developed via GitHub and documented including Readmes. Data and software are covered by copyright; most are expected to be made freely available under specific licences (e.g. Creative Commons CC-BY). The Prediction tool software developed in WP4 will be freely available but licensed for use to end-users.

5.2 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

WHAT WILL THE COSTS BE FOR MAKING DATA OR OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS FAIR IN YOUR PROJECT (E.G. DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS RELATED TO STORAGE, ARCHIVING, RE-USE, SECURITY, ETC.)?

In the context of our consortium, all partners allocate dedicated human resources and utilise their own infrastructures to manage data. Since this curating activity (storage, archiving, re-use, security) is also dependent on the amount and type of data that will be effectively collected, detailed expenditure information will be provided in subsequent releases of this plan.

5.3 DATA SECURITY

WHAT PROVISIONS ARE OR WILL BE IN PLACE FOR DATA SECURITY (INCLUDING DATA RECOVERY AS WELL AS SECURE STORAGE/ARCHIVING AND TRANSFER OF SENSITIVE DATA)?

Produced or processed research data (during the production process, i.e. premature to publication) from this project will be securely stored by all project partners in individual storage facility solutions, such as:

- cloud solutions
- institutional repositories
- institutional servers/databases

Cloud solutions used by partners are:

- Microsoft OneDrive
- Microsoft Sharepoint
- Google Drive

All the partners using cloud solutions have special agreements with providers on privacy and information security legislation and guidelines to comply with the GDPR, e.g. storage of data on European servers.

Institutional repositories, clouds, servers and databases such as:

1. Digital.CSIC (<https://digital.csic.es/>) The institutional repository of CSIC
2. Further institutional repositories will be detailed in the forthcoming releases of this deliverable.

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The institutional storage solutions are part of the University/company infrastructure and comply with privacy and security policies of the concerning institutes.

These facilities allow storage of large data volumes that are backed up on a daily basis, in specialised data centres, not only ensuring the preservation of the data in a trustworthy and dependable location, but also effectively minimising the risk of data loss in the event of any system malfunction or crash.

The used storage facility solutions handle data access based on the principle of "need-to-know". This means that only users who require access to the data for their work or tasks are authorised to access it. Every data user can access-log in these facilities with personal-institutional credentials.

The analysed or resulted data of the project will be published on well-known and trusted repositories (i.e. Zenodo, NCBI etc., see above) and therefore they will be secure through the security provisions of these platforms.

While transfer of sensitive research data does not apply in the project, the use of secure institutional systems can provide assurance against any unanticipated attempts at data tampering, whether deliberate or accidental in nature.

5.4 ETHICS

ARE THERE, OR COULD THERE BE, ANY ETHICS OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON DATA SHARING? THESE CAN ALSO BE DISCUSSED IN THE CONTEXT OF THE ETHICS REVIEW. IF RELEVANT, INCLUDE REFERENCES TO ETHICS DELIVERABLES AND ETHICS CHAPTER IN THE DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTION (DOA).

The AquaPLAN consortium will ensure all research activities are conducted in compliance with fundamental ethical principles and within European and national laws and norms. Ethical issues shall be considered in four main types of activities: i) Personal contact data collection for the stakeholder engagement and communication and outreach (WP2, 5, 6); ii) Interviews with (groups of) stakeholders (WP2, 5); iii) Experiments on animals (fish, invertebrates, marine mammals); iv) Participation of Third countries (UK, Australia). AquaPLAN will deliver mandatory deliverable reports on all ethical issues, providing detailed responses to the ethical issues raised regarding personal data collected and experiments on animals. It will provide the necessary information on the informed consent procedures used for stakeholder engagement and contain consent forms needed for personal data collection and interviews. It will also include the data protection policies of the Consortium partners and those set for the project, describing the approach to how data will be handled and what research rules and principles will be applied (organisational, national and on an international level). It will also contain details of all experiments on animals. If any documents, such as certification/approval letters approving experiments to be conducted of experiments according to the national regulation, will be required, Partners will apply for them prior to the experimental work and provide copies to the coordinator, who can submit the documents to EC and Agencies anytime on request.

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WILL INFORMED CONSENT FOR DATA SHARING AND LONG TERM PRESERVATION BE INCLUDED IN QUESTIONNAIRES DEALING WITH PERSONAL DATA?

All personal data from T2.2 and T5.3 will be collected, held and analysed by PML in the UK, and as such falls within the legal remit of The Data protection Act (2018) UK. Some personal contact details will also be stored during WP1 led by UNIPI (IT), and WP6 led by ERINN (IE). These activities fall within the legal remit of the GDPR 2016/679. Personal data, such as emails, will be stored separately from datasets. All personal data will be kept securely (under encrypted server and password protected) and will be published in aggregate or anonymized (including publication on the internet), thus it will not lead to a breach of agreed confidentiality and anonymity (stated in an informed consent form at start of all surveys). The collection, storage and use of personal data will be made fair, transparent and accountable to all participants prior to participation.

5.5 OTHER ISSUES

DO YOU, OR WILL YOU, MAKE USE OF OTHER NATIONAL/FUNDER/SECTORIAL/DEPARTMENTAL PROCEDURES FOR DATA MANAGEMENT? IF YES, WHICH ONES (PLEASE LIST AND BRIEFLY DESCRIBE THEM)?

No. We only follow the data management procedures provided by the European Commission (Horizon Europe Template).

5.6 ACTIVITY PLAN FOR DATA MANAGEMENT

Table 1. Activity Plan for Data management.

Task	Activities	Responsible and other partners	By when / Status
T1.4 Data management (M1-M48) Lead: UNIPI	First release of Data Management Plan (D 1.4) with all consortium members	UNIPI, all	June 2024 (M6)
	Second release of Data Management Plan (D1.5) with all consortium members	UNIPI, all	December 2025 (M24)
	Third release of Data Management Plan (D 1.6) with all consortium members	UNIPI, all	December 2027 (M48)

DELIVERABLES:

D1.4 Data Management Plan, 1st release – M6 (UNIPI)

D1.5 Data Management Plan, 2nd release – M24 (UNIPI)

D1.6 Data Management Plan, 3rd release – M48 (UNIPI)

MILESTONES:

None of the 8 milestones as listed in the GA (page 32) directly cites the Data Management Plan.

6. Annex

6.1 TABLES OF PRODUCED DATA

Produced data will be listed with all necessary information in an excel-table, named DMP_Data_Produced_VX.xlsx (where the VX stands for version number X). The table will be regularly updated and given a new version number. The table is available to all consortium members in the Google Drive Intranet. The template of the table for produced data sets has the form:

Table 2. Table of produced data

DATASET/RELATED TASK	DATA TYPE	SIZE	FINDABILITY & ACCESSIBILITY	INTEROPERABILITY	REUSABILITY
Literature database of LNP impacts on aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem services (T2.1)	Database	1GB	OA: AquaPLAN web page	.csv .dbf .xlsx .doc	CC BY 4.0, English
Stakeholders' perceptions and knowledge of LNP in Europe (T2.2)	Table	5 GB	OA: PML data portal or UK data service	.csv	CC BY 4.0, English
Review of the implementation of MSFD by EU Member states (T2.2)	Text	5 GB	OA: PML data portal or UK data service	.csv	CC BY 4.0, English
International, EU and non-EU legal framework for tackling the impacts of LNP (T2.2)	Database	5 GB	OA: PML data portal or UK data service	.dbf .xlsx .csv .txt	CC BY 4.0, English
EC wide ALAN intensities; coasts, lakes (T3.1)	Map	10 GB	OA: Pangaea with DOI	netCDF	CC BY 4.0, English
EC wide noise, shipping (T3.1)	Map	10 GB	OA: Pangaea with DOI	netCDF	CC BY 4.0, English
EC wide combined stressor ALAN and Noise, habitats (T3.1)	Map	10 GB	OA: Pangaea with DOI	netCDF	CC BY 4.0, English
Maps of impacts of ALAN and noise pollution on key marine species (T3.2)	Map	1 GB	OA: Pangaea with DOI	geotiff	CC BY 4.0, English
Database of ecological time series relating biodiversity changes to LNP pollution conditions (including EBVs responses and data on stressors) (T3.3)	Database	1 GB	OA: Dryad with DOI	.csv .dbf .xlsx	CC BY 4.0, English
Database of ecological time series of eDNA of invertebrate's biodiversity under	Database	10 GB	OA: Dryad with DOI	fastq, csv .dbf .xlsx	CC BY 4.0, English

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DATASET/RELATED TASK	DATA TYPE	SIZE	FINDABILITY & ACCESSIBILITY	INTEROPERABILITY	REUSABILITY
ALAN and noise pollution conditions in tropical coral reef ecosystem (T3.3)					
Passive acoustic data of the acoustic diversity of the seagrass <i>P. oceanica</i> in the Mediterranean in relation to the response to crossed LNP effects. Data on the healthy status of the seagrass (T4.1)	Audio and table	500 GB	OA: Dryad with DOI	.csv .mp3	CC BY 4.0, English
Physiological, behavioral and molecular data of the impacts of LNP on corals biology and damselfish sleeping and health behavior (T4.1)	Images, video and tables	100 GB	OA: Dryad with DOI	.csv .mp4	CC BY 4.0, English
Recordings of marine soundscapes from urbanised estuaries and coastal waters along metropolitan coastlines, and corresponding recruitment data of larvae (T4.1)	Audio and table	1 GB	OA: Dryad with DOI	.xlsx .csv .wav	CC BY 4.0, English
Video recordings of the thermographic camera capturing seabirds attending fishing vessels with different lighting systems (T4.2)	Video	10 GB	OA: Digital CSIC	.mp4	CC BY 4.0, English
Video Recording of whales at surface during exposure experiments (T4.2)	Video	100 GB	OA: Norwegian Marine Datacenter	.mp4 .avi	CC BY 4.0, English
Sound recording from whale tags (T4.2)	Audio	50 GB	OA: Norwegian Marine Datacenter	.wav	CC BY 4.0, English
Movement data from whale tags (T4.2)	Table	5 GB	OA: Norwegian Marine Datacenter	.csv	CC BY 4.0, English
Echosounder data showing fish distribution during exposure experiments (T4.2)	Video	100 GB	OA: Norwegian Marine Datacenter	.avi	CC BY 4.0, English
Zooplankton images with Mini Deep-focus Plankton Imager (MDPI) from different aquatic sites (T4.3)	Images, Tables	0.1 TB	OA: Archived on local servers hosted at FVB-IGB	.dng .csv	CC BY 4.0, English
Underwater LNP profiles from different aquatic sites (T4.3)	Table	100 MB	OA: Archived on local servers hosted at FVB-IGB	.xlsx .txt .csv	CC BY 4.0, English

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DATASET/RELATED TASK	DATA TYPE	SIZE	FINDABILITY & ACCESSIBILITY	INTEROPERABILITY	REUSABILITY
Level of onset of adverse biological effects (LOBE) values for pelagic and benthic invertebrates in EU waters, and threshold GES values (T5.1)	Table	100 MB	OA: Dryad with DOI	.csv .xlsx .txt .dbf	CC BY 4.0, English
Maps of the exposure and risk presented by ALAN to important, vulnerable and protected habitats in European seas (T5.1)	Map	1 GB	OA: Pangaea with DOI	geotiff	CC BY 4.0, English
Database of existing and potential LNP mitigation measures (T5.2)	Database	1 GB	OA: Dryad with DOI	.dbf .csv .xlsx	CC BY 4.0, English
Choice experiment survey data on mitigation preference and barriers (T5.3)	Table	2 GB	OA: PML data portal or UK data service	.csv	CC BY 4.0, English

6.2 ACRONYMS

Table 3. List of acronyms.

Acronym	Full
CA	Consortium Agreement
DDBJ	DNA DataBank of Japan
DM/DMP	data management/ Data Management Plan
FAIR	findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation (of EU)
IP	Intellectual property
SIB	Stakeholder Innovation Board
WP	work package

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Project Coordinator

Elena Maggi | elena.maggi@unipi.it

Press and Communications

Avril Hanbidge | avril@erinn.eu

More Information

Website | aquaplan-project.eu

X | [@AquaPLAN_EU](https://twitter.com/AquaPLAN_EU)

LinkedIn | [@AquaPLAN Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/AquaPLAN-Project)